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SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL BASES OF LOAD STANDARDIZATION IN MASS SPORTS HEALTH TRAINING

Mukhametov Akhmad Mukhametovich

Professor of the "Physical culture and sports activity" department
Tashkent State University of Economics

***Abstract.** The article provides a classification, a brief summary of various directions, structure and methodological features of conducting health aerobics classes. A description of the basic elements of aerobics, their terminology and combination options is provided.*

***Keywords:** Mass sport, standardization, method, technology, physics.*

INTRODUCTION

At present, the interest of young people in various types of mass sports and physical activity for recreation and recuperation, to ensure good physical fitness and health has increased significantly. Fitness clubs equipped with modern exercise machines, new types of fitness aerobics classes, festivals, conventions - all these areas contribute to the development and maintenance of interest in health-improving activities. Among these health-improving trainings, aerobics has taken a special place. Health-improving aerobics is distinguished by the emotional richness of the classes, the simplicity and variability of the means used, the ability to control and self-control the health of those involved, musicality, plasticity and danceability of the exercises performed. In their unity, the components of aerobics can ensure the achievement of socially significant results: health, physical development, culture of movement, aesthetics of the physical image; preserve and develop individual character traits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research shows that aerobic exercise improves the health of the body. People who regularly engage in health aerobics show an increase in aerobic performance and endurance. These positive changes include an improvement in the vital capacity of the lungs, blood volume and hemoglobin level, stroke volume and minute volume of blood circulation. Aerobic exercise increases the fibrinolytic activity of the blood, which ensures lysis, i.e. dissolution, of blood clots. The capillary network, lumen and elasticity of the capillaries increase, resulting in a decrease in peripheral resistance to blood flow and a decrease in blood pressure. Changes in the capillary network occur not only in muscle tissue, but also in the heart muscle, brain, liver and other organs and tissues involved in muscle work. The permeability of the walls of blood vessels for oxygen, nutrients, and metabolic products increases. All this creates more favorable conditions for metabolic processes in tissues.

Health aerobic programs attract a wide range of people because of their accessibility, emotionality, and the ability to change the content of lessons depending on their interests and preparedness. The basis of any lesson is various exercises performed in walking, running, jumping, as well as strength and flexibility exercises performed from different starting positions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

the content of the exercise complexes and meet the principle of "safe technique" for performing them: steps and their variations, running in place and with movements, lifting the hips in different directions, leg swings, lunges, jumping with a change in the position of the legs, "skip" - cross movements.

In connection with the specifics of aerobics, the following means are most typical for lessons:

1. General development exercises

1.1. In a standing position [1]:

— exercises for the arms and shoulder girdle in different directions (lifting-lowering, flexion-extension, arcs and circles);

— exercises for the torso and neck (bends and turns, forward arc movements);

1.2. In a sitting and lying position:

— exercises for the feet (alternating and simultaneous flexion and extension, circular movements);

- exercises for the legs in a lying position and in a kneeling position (flexion-extension, lifting-lowering, swings);

- exercises for the abdominal muscles while lying on your back (raising the shoulders and shoulder blades, also with a turn of the torso, raising the legs - bent or extended);

— exercises for the back muscles in a prone position and in a kneeling position (small amplitude of raising the arms, legs or simultaneous movements of the arms and legs with “stretching” in length) [2].

Types of aerobic steps used in health programs often have several variants of names. Here are the existing variants of the terms in English and their terminological names in Russian.

These include:

1. **KNEE LIFT** (Knee lift, Knee up). From the starting position, standing on one leg (straight), bend the other leg forward above the horizontal (any angle in the knee joint is allowed), the toe is pulled back. The body should be kept in a vertical position. The rotation of the pelvis accompanying the movement of the raised leg is not allowed. When raising the knee, any movement variant can be used (standing in place, moving in any direction, turning, walking, running, jumping).

2. **KICK** is performed in a standing position on one leg. The straight swinging leg is raised straight forward, a slight "turnout" position of the foot is allowed, but without the rotation of the pelvis accompanying the swing. The swing amplitude is determined by the level of training of the practitioner; a "whip-like" movement and uncontrolled lowering of the leg after the swing (falling) are not allowed. The minimum amplitude in sports aerobics can be considered a swing above the horizontal level, but for the health direction of aerobics, the swing amplitude is recommended to be no higher than 90°. It is allowed to use any combination of leg swing with movements in place, steps, running, jumping. Different planes of movement are also possible - swing forward, forward - to the side (diagonally) or to the side. If the swing is combined with a jump, then upon landing it is necessary to land on the entire foot, avoid ballistic landings and loss of balance. Low kick - a type of shin swing. It is performed in 2 counts. 1 - bending the knee, raise the right leg forward - down (the swing can be performed in any direction - forward, diagonally, back). At the moment of extension of the knee joint of the right leg, swing the shin. 2 - return to the starting position [3].

3. **JUMPING JACK WITH LEGS APART - LEGS TOGETHER** (Jumping jack, Hampelmann) is performed from the starting position with feet together (heels together, toes slightly apart - foot-width apart). The movement consists of two main parts. The first is to push off with both feet, jump up not very high and then assume a

half-squat position with feet apart (feet slightly turned outward or parallel), landing on the entire foot. The distance between the feet is equal to the width of the shoulders, the body weight is evenly distributed on both legs, the direction of the knees and feet should match. During this movement, the projection of the knees should not go beyond the support of the feet, the angle in the knee joints should be more than 90° . The second part of the movement is to join the legs with a small jump and return to the starting position. When performing this movement, torso movements (bending, turning) are not allowed

4. LUNG can be performed in any way (step, jump, after a swing), and also in different directions (forward, sideways, backwards). The basic version of this "aerobic step" is the forward lunge position. In this case, the weight of the body shifts to the bent leg, extended forward. The angle in the knee joint should be greater than 90° , the shin of the supporting leg is located close to the vertical position, and the projection of the knee does not go beyond the support of the foot (it is necessary to land on the heel of the supporting leg) [4].

Pelvic rotation is not allowed, the leg behind should be straight, touching the floor with the toe, the heel raised (up).

5. STEP (March) resembles natural walking, but is more precise. Standing on a straight leg (torso vertical), bend the other leg and raise it straight forward (knee below horizontal position), without turning the pelvis accompanying the movement. The foot of the raised leg is at the level of the upper third of the shin, the toe is pulled back (i.e. the ankle joint is bent). Marching — walking in place, Walking — walking in different directions, forward and backward, in a circle, diagonally.

6. RUNNING (Jog) — transition from one leg to another as when walking, but with a flight phase. Jogging — a variant of running, like a "jog".

7. Jumps (Skip, rick kick). The main movement is performed in the rhythm of "AND - ONE" or "ONE - TWO".

Basic Step — basic step. Performed in 4 counts: 1 — step forward with the right foot, 2 — put the left one forward, 3 — step back with the right foot, 4 — put the left one forward [5].

CONCLUSION

So: 1) the safety of aerobic training implies both the correct selection of exercises and the compilation of complexes, as well as the appropriate technique of execution, in particular:

- when performing movements, abrupt ballistic movements should be avoided;
- it is necessary to change the working link or direction of movement every 8 counts;
- the change in the amplitude and power of the movement should be gradual both in the direction of increase and decrease;

2) new movements or methods of movement should be performed at a slow pace or even imitated;

3) to facilitate execution, it is effective to use accompanying commands and prompts in word and action – demonstration

Health aerobics classes affect the somatic and mental spheres of a person, increase vigor and help to gain confidence in one's abilities.

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